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DriftMoE: A Mixture of Experts Approach to Handle Concept Drifts

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PROBLEM & MOTIVATION

Existing ensemble methods for concept drift rely on coarse-grained adaptation and fail to optimally leverage specialized knowledge.

Challenges

- (1) Active methods rely on explicit drift detection which can be delayed or generate false positives
- (2) Passive methods use simple voting schemes that don't leverage expert specialization
- (3) Most approaches lack principled mechanisms for experts to develop specialized knowledge

Solutions

- (1) Symbiotic co-training framework without explicit drift detection
- (2) Neural router that dynamically assigns data to most suitable experts
- (3) Multi-hot correctness mask enables principled expert specialization

Main Findings:

We introduce the first Mixture of Experts framework specifically designed for real-time data streams with concept drift.

- achieves competitive performance with fewer trees than traditional ensembles.

- adapts in real-time through novel symbiotic router-expert co-training.

DriftMoE outperforms state-of-the-art methods like ARF and Leveraging Bagging while using only 12 experts instead of 100+ trees.

SOLUTION & OVERVIEW

DriftMoE Framework:

- Online MoE architecture
- Co-training approach
- Neural router + experts

Two Variants:

- **MoE-Data (multi-class):** Router selects Top-K experts based on learned weights
- **MoE-Task (one-vs-rest):** All experts activated with binary labels

SOLUTION & OVERVIEW

Symbiotic Training Process

1

Router Selection

MoE-Data: Router selects Top-K experts based on learned weights

MoE-Task: All experts activated with binary labels

2

Expert Updates

Selected experts make predictions and update incrementally using Hoeffding tree learning rules

3

Correctness Mask

Multi-hot mask generated: $m_{t,i} = 1$ if expert i predicts correctly, 0 otherwise

4

Router Update

Router parameters refined using binary cross-entropy loss with correctness feedback in mini-batches

KEY FEATURES & ARCHITECTURE

Symbiotic Training

Router and experts co-evolve through continuous feedback loops, enabling dynamic specialization without explicit drift detection.

Resource Efficient

Achieves competitive performance with significantly fewer base learners compared to traditional ensemble methods.

Two Variants

MoE-Data (multi-class experts) and MoE-Task (binary experts) configurations for different specialization strategies.

DriftMoE Framework:

- Multi-hot correctness
- mask training
- Cooperative feedback
- Symbiotic learning
- Resource efficiency: Cooperative feedback 12 vs 100+ experts

Technical Details:

- Hoeffding Tree experts
- BCE loss optimization
- Online mini-batches

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Datasets Evaluated

Synthetic:

- LED (Abrupt/Gradual)
- SEA (Abrupt/Gradual)
- RBF (Moderate/Fast)

Real-world:

- Airlines
- Electricity
- CoverType

Table 1: Datasets.

Category	Stream	Instances	Features	Classes
Synthetic	LED (Abrupt)	1,000,000	24	10
	LED (Gradual)	1,000,000	24	10
	SEA (Abrupt)	1,000,000	3	2
	SEA (Gradual)	1,000,000	3	2
	RBF_m	1,000,000	10	5
	RBF_f	1,000,000	10	5
Real	Airlines	539,383	7	2
	Electricity	45,312	8	2
	Cover Type	581,012	54	7

EXPERIMENTS

Dataset specifications

Prequential accuracy comparison across nine benchmark datasets.

Baselines Compared

- Adaptive Random Forest (ARF)
- Leveraging Bagging (LevBag)
- OzaBag, OzaBoost, SmoothBoost
- Streaming Random Patches (SRP)

Dataset	MoE-Data	MoE-Task
Airlines	70.33 ± 0.18	60.92 ± 0.01
CovType	81.28 ± 0.75	58.28 ± 0.31
Electricity	83.76 ± 0.45	68.73 ± 0.85
LED _a	73.77 ± 0.18	71.11 ± 0.54
LED _g	73.11 ± 0.11	70.82 ± 0.38
RBF _f	61.90 ± 0.20	75.45 ± 0.11
RBF _m	79.89 ± 0.48	88.65 ± 0.07
SEA _a	89.09 ± 0.05	88.04 ± 0.09
SEA _g	88.74 ± 0.05	87.76 ± 0.04

EXPERIMENTS

Prequential accuracy comparison across nine benchmark datasets.

DriftMoE variants achieve competitive performance with state-of-the-art adaptive ensembles across synthetic and real-world streams.

EXPERIMENTS

Concept Drift Adaptation

DriftMoE demonstrates fast recovery after concept drift points, matching the adaptation speed of larger ensembles.

Accuracy over time for LED gradual drift dataset.

KEY FINDINGS

Summary:

- **MoE-Data:** Most robust across datasets, achieves 70.33 ± 0.18 on Airlines (best among all methods)
- **MoE-Task:** Excels in high-frequency drift scenarios (75.45 ± 0.11 on RBFf, 88.65 ± 0.07 on RBFm)
- **Efficiency:** Less resources. Competitive with SOTA methods using significantly fewer base learners (12 vs 100+ trees)
- **Fast Recovery:** Fast drift adaptation. Matches ADWIN-equipped ensemble recovery speed after concept drift

Main Contributions:

- First streaming MoE for concept drift
- Novel co-training framework
- Multi-hot feedback
- Competitive performance with fewer resources

Deployment:

- Resource-constrained environments
- Real-time inference
- Adaptive edge devices
- Streaming analytics

DISCUSSIONS

Impact:

- Scalable continual learning
- Efficient drift handling

Applications:

- IoT data streams
- Financial markets
- Social media feeds
- Edge computing

Future Directions:

- Uncertainty routing
- Dynamic allocation
- Cost-sensitive losses

Thank you

Project page

Paper

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